

CEO Confidence Index

A quarterly survey measuring the confidence of Canadian business leaders of small-to-medium enterprises.

Q1 2024

ANALYSIS by Dr. Peter Andersen Economist

Our TEC Canada CEO Confidence Survey is an economic barometer for small and medium-sized Canadian businesses. TEC is a unique organization which brings members together to discuss issues, opportunities, and the way forward.

The TEC Canada 1st Quarter 2024 CEO Confidence Survey summarizes the latest thinking on business conditions, market challenges and opportunities, company performance, and management plans.

It also allows a tracking on how TEC CEOs have responded over time, in previous surveys, to the unfolding business cycle. There have indeed been major swings in business confidence since the first survey was carried out in the spring of 2018.

The latest survey was closed off on December 22nd. This is basically as close to real-time information as you can get. With a high response from approximately 400 TEC CEOs, the survey results provide a valuable insight into business confidence, for a key sector of Canada's economy.

Survey Respondents

The respondents surveyed for this report are members of TEC Canada, representing a diverse range of Canadian business leaders. This inclusive group comprises of owners, CEOs and senior executives from small to mid-sized companies across various industries. From manufacturing and engineering to pharmaceuticals, transportation, food, and more, the membership base reflects a broad spectrum of expertise.

This diversity extends beyond industry lines to cover the geographical breadth of the nation, with members situated from coast to coast. This varied representation ensures the formation of TEC

groups that draw upon a rich mix of perspectives, enhancing leadership development, mentorship, and peer advisory collaboration.

TEC Canada leverages this diversity to provide a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by business leaders in today's evolving landscape. The collaborative exchange of insights fosters strategic thinking and equips members to navigate the complexities of their industries with agility and resilience. In essence, TEC Canada's diverse and widespread membership base forms a dynamic community where leadership excellence is not only nurtured but celebrated across sectors and regions.

TECCANADA CEO Confidence Index Q1 2024

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For **63%** of TEC leaders, business conditions have worsened over the last twelve months.

Provincial Expectations: Worsening Conditions

37% B. C.

- 21% BETTER
- 37% ABOUT THE SAME
- 5% DON'T KNOW/NO OPINION

41% Alberta

- 11% BETTER
- 44% ABOUT THE SAME
- 4% DON'T KNOW/NO OPINION

44% Ontario

- 18% BETTER
- 36% ABOUT THE SAME
- 2% DON'T KNOW/NO OPINION

62% Quebec

- 7% BETTER
- 31% ABOUT THE SAME
- 0% DON'T KNOW/NO OPINION

Economic Outlook

The survey update shows that the belt-tightening reported last fall is continuing. A weaker economy, high interest rates, and tighter credit conditions are taking their toll on business confidence, for small and medium-sized firms.

Last year was a tough one, with a sizeable majority (63%) saying that business conditions worsened over the

12 months ending December. Some provinces were particularly hard hit. In BC 75% report a worsening. Quebec is close at 71%.

Looking ahead, at the national level, a high percentage of respondents (45%) expect another year of deteriorating economic conditions in 2024. Quebec is again an outlier with 62% expecting a worsening.

417 leaders were polled with this first question—during the next 12 months, do you expect overall economic conditions in Canada will be better, about the same, or worse than now?

Despite continued calls for economic headwinds, the pessimistic expectations of TEC leaders show some early signs of softening compared to a year ago. Caution remains the priority, with business expectations remaining resilient for now.

Questions to Consider

Reflect on these critical questions as you read the report, and discuss them with your organization's Leadership Team.

1

Have your economic expectations for 2024 started to shift? How has this affected your strategy? How has this affected your customers' or suppliers' strategies?

2

How many price increases have you done over the last year? How many more do you plan to do? Are there any blind spots or limits on passing costs on to customers through price increases?

3

Are you expecting interest rates to be cut in 2024? Is this influencing any of your investment or expenditure plans? What are the risks involved?

Profitability, Pricing, & Operational Costs

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As a result of supply-side improvements and a weak economy, a majority (56%) now expect the Bank of Canada to begin cutting interest rates, either this spring or summer.

A near majority of TEC CEOs across Canada (48%) expect their firms' price-adjusted volume revenue to increase in 2024. The outlook for firms' revenues is slightly better in Ontario and Alberta, where 52% in each province expect an increase over the next 12 months.

The outlook for profitability and business fixed investment is holding up, with 74% expecting profits to stay the same or improve, and an even higher percentage (79%) expecting this for investment. This outlook for profitability partly reflects the belief that cost increases can be passed on to consumers.

Despite concern about a worsening economy, a high percentage (45%) believe that they have the ability to pass on costs to customers by increasing selling prices. In addition, 24% say they are not sure. Only 31% think that they would not be able to pass costs on to customers.

Just over half expect to increase their firms' selling prices over the next 12 months. Only 7% expect to cut prices. Market conditions are softer

in Quebec, where only 38% plan on price increases and 14% plan to cut prices. In contrast, in BC 61% expect their prices to increase.

Compensation costs (wages, salaries, and benefits) are reported by many to be running at a high rate, in the 4% to 5% range (50%), or even higher (26%). More than half expect to increase employee compensation in the next three months.

Despite such labour cost inflation pressure, TEC CEO inflation expectations are coming down. The median 1-year inflation expectation of survey respondents is now in the 3% range, down from 4% in the previous survey, three months earlier.

Supply chain shortages are reported by 72% to have diminished. Despite a positive outlook for firms' sales volumes, the majority (76% where applicable) do not feel a need to add to inventories in 2024.

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74%

of respondents report that they are expecting profits to stay the same or improve.

Even higher percentage (79%) are expecting this for investment.

45%

believe they will be able to pass on costs to customers by increasing selling prices.

3%

is the median 1-year inflation expectation.

Down from 4% in the Q4 2023 survey.

Employment & Hiring Intentions

The percentage saying no change in employment levels is down to 38% from 44% three months earlier.

There is still a high percentage (61%) reporting that it is not getting easier to fill open jobs. However a sizeable number (39%) do actually report that job openings are not as hard to fill.

TEC firms are now a bit more cautious on hiring. More are planning to decrease employment now (14% versus 10% in the previous survey). The percentage saying no change in employment levels is down to 38% from 44% three months earlier.

These are small changes that show a shift at the margin. The main message is still that demand for workers is still holding up. Approximately half of TEC CEOs (47%) plan to increase payroll employment over the next 12 months.

A consistent message in our surveys has been that layoffs are not likely. However the latest survey results suggest that while the main message still holds, there are shifts under the surface.

Most responses (64%) still indicate that there will be no layoffs. However 29% are now either undertaking layoffs or are considering them. This compares with 23% three months ago. In BC 34% are either undertaking or considering them.

64%

are not planning layoffs.

29% are recently undertaking or considering layoffs.

Demand for workers is still holding up.

47%

of surveyed business leaders plan to increase payroll employment over the next 12 months

Recession Outlook

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The absence of widespread layoffs is a key reason why a “soft landing” is a possible outcome in 2024. This would be slow growth but not an outright contraction. The ability to stay employed has allowed consumers and homeowners to withstand the impact of current high interest rates.

While all TEC CEOs anticipate economic headwinds in 2024, a sizeable high percentage (39%) believe that we are already in a soft landing, or will soon be in one.

However, while the hard data on firms’ revenues and profitability are positive, confidence in the economy is under a cloud.

A majority (58%) believe that Canada is either already in a recession, or will be soon in 2024. This view is widespread across the country, with Alberta at 54%, Ontario 59%, Quebec 60%, and BC at 63%.

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believe that Canada is either already in a recession, or will be soon in 2024.

Percentage is highest among BC CEOs (63%).

Despite anticipating economic headwinds,

39%

of our respondents believe that we are already in a soft landing, or will soon be in one.

Survey Results

The TEC Canada CEO Confidence Index is a quarterly survey measuring the confidence of Canadian business leaders of small-to-medium enterprises. The results provide insight into the challenges and opportunities faced by leaders and their confidence in the Canadian business environment. The TEC CEO Confidence Index Q1 2024 was conducted from November 24th to December 22nd, 2023, and had 417 Canadian participants in the research.

Question	Answer	Canada		BC		Alberta		Ontario		QC	
		%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total
Q5 Are your firm's total fixed investment expenditures likely to increase, remain about the same, or decrease during the next 12 months?	INCREASE	34.94	138	42.11	24	35.23	31	33.06	40	33.33	14
	REMAIN THE SAME	43.8	173	45.61	26	43.18	38	42.15	51	45.24	19
	DECREASE	18.99	75	10.53	6	18.18	16	23.14	28	21.43	9
	DON'T KNOW/NO OPINION	2.28	9	1.75	1	3.41	3	1.65	2	0	0

Q6 Do you expect your firm's total number of employees will increase, remain about the same, or decrease during the next 12 months?	INCREASE	46.91	182	42.11	24	53.41	47	47.93	58	38.1	16
	REMAIN THE SAME	37.89	147	49.12	28	35.23	31	37.19	45	35.71	15
	DECREASE	13.92	54	7.02	4	11.36	10	14.05	17	26.19	11
	DON'T KNOW/NO OPINION	1.29	5	1.75	1	0	0	0.83	1	0	0

Question	Answer	Canada		BC		Alberta		Ontario		QC	
		%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total
Q7 Do you expect prices for your product or service to increase, remain about the same, or decrease during the next 12 months?	INCREASE	51.28	201	61.4	35	48.86	43	49.59	60	38.1	16
	REMAIN THE SAME	41.58	163	33.33	19	47.73	42	41.32	50	47.62	20
	DECREASE	6.89	27	5.26	3	3.41	3	8.26	10	14.29	6
	DON'T KNOW/NO OPINION	0.26	1	0	0	0	0	0.83	1	0	0
Q8 Do you believe that your firm will have the ability to pass on cost increases to customers through increasing prices for your products or services?	YES	44.96	174	40.35	23	47.13	41	45.45	55	45.24	19
	NO	31.01	120	26.32	15	36.78	32	32.23	39	30.95	13
	NOT SURE	24.03	93	33.33	19	16.09	14	22.31	27	23.81	10
Q9 Have you considered or undertaken layoffs in response to economic uncertainty?	YES - I AM CONSIDERING LAYOFFS	17.05	66	22.81	13	18.18	16	14.88	18	16.67	7
	YES - CURRENTLY UNDERTAKING LAYOFFS	11.89	46	10.53	6	6.82	6	14.88	18	19.05	8
	NO	64.08	248	59.65	34	67.05	59	61.98	75	59.52	25
	NOT SURE	6.98	27	7.02	4	7.95	7	8.26	10	4.76	2

Question	Answer	Canada		BC		Alberta		Ontario		QC	
		%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total
Q10 What is your current assessment of the Canadian economy?	ALREADY EXPERIENCED A SOFT LANDING	13.58	55	12.07	7	15.22	14	15.45	19	16.28	7
	A SOFT LANDING IS COMING	25.43	103	24.14	14	28.26	26	22.76	28	20.93	9
	CURRENTLY IN A RECESSION	31.11	126	34.48	20	21.74	20	39.02	48	23.26	10
	A RECESSION IS COMING	27.41	111	27.59	16	31.52	29	20.33	25	37.21	16
	OTHER	2.47	10	1.72	1	3.26	3	2.44	3	2.33	1
Q11 What is your 1-year ahead expectation for inflation?	5%	11.95	46	14.04	8	11.36	10	14.88	18	4.76	2
	4%	36.1	139	35.09	20	45.45	40	28.1	34	42.86	18
	3%	43.9	169	45.61	26	36.36	32	47.11	57	45.24	19
	2%	8.05	31	5.26	3	6.82	6	9.92	12	7.14	3
Q12 How has the difficulty of filling open jobs at your company changed compared to a year ago?	EASIER TO FILL ROLES	38.96	150	42.11	24	29.55	26	46.28	56	45.24	19
	NO CHANGE	40	154	49.12	28	42.05	37	30.58	37	47.62	20
	MORE DIFFICULT TO FILL ROLES	21.04	81	8.77	5	28.41	25	23.14	28	7.14	3
Q13 When do you expect the Bank of Canada to begin cutting rates?	BEFORE MID-YEAR 2024	27.01	104	29.82	17	29.55	26	26.45	32	23.81	10
	SUMMER 2024	29.09	112	21.05	12	27.27	24	35.54	43	30.95	13
	FALL 2024	20	77	19.3	11	21.59	19	18.18	22	19.05	8
	IN 2025 OR LATER	17.92	69	24.56	14	14.77	13	15.7	19	23.81	10
	NOT SURE	5.97	23	5.26	3	6.82	6	4.13	5	2.38	1

Question	Answer	Canada		BC		Alberta		Ontario		QC	
		%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total
Q14 What year over year rates of increase are you experiencing in your firm's compensation costs (wages, salaries, benefits)?	OVER 5%	25.91	100	40.35	23	15.91	14	28.1	34	26.19	11
	4% TO 5%	50.26	194	36.84	21	53.41	47	49.59	60	64.29	27
	LESS THAN 3%	20.73	80	19.3	11	29.55	26	18.18	22	7.14	3
	NO CHANGE	3.11	12	3.51	2	1.14	1	4.13	5	2.38	1
Q15 Do you plan to increase compensation in the next 3 months?	YES	53.91	207	51.79	29	55.68	49	57.85	70	50	21
	NO	39.06	150	37.5	21	38.64	34	39.67	48	35.71	15
	NOT SURE	7.03	27	10.71	6	5.68	5	2.48	3	14.29	6
Q16 Are you experiencing supply chain shortages of non-labour inputs?	YES	22.08	85	28.07	16	20.45	18	21.49	26	7.14	3
	NO	71.95	277	68.42	39	69.32	61	73.55	89	88.1	37
	NOT SURE	5.97	23	3.51	2	10.23	9	4.96	6	4.76	2
Q17 Do you expect that you will be growing your inventories in 2024?	YES	12.89	50	8.77	5	18.18	16	10.74	13	11.9	5
	NO	56.7	220	70.18	40	46.59	41	54.55	66	66.67	28
	NOT SURE	4.64	18	7.02	4	5.68	5	4.13	5	2.38	1
	NOT APPLICABLE	25.77	100	14.04	8	29.55	26	30.58	37	19.05	8

Question	Answer	Canada		BC		Alberta		Ontario		QC	
		%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total
Q18 What province or territory is your business located in?	BRITISH COLUMBIA	13.67	57	100	57	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ALBERTA	21.10	88	0	0	100	88	0	0	0	0
	SASKATCHEWAN	4.08	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	MANITOBA	1.44	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ONTARIO	29.02	121	0	0	0	0	100	121	0	0
	QUEBEC	11.99	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	50
	NEW BRUNSWICK	0.48	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	NOVA SCOTIA	0.96	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	UNKNOWN	17.27	72	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Dr. Peter Andersen, Economist

Dr. Peter Andersen is an independent consulting economist specializing in economic forecasting. He obtained his doctorate in economics from Harvard University. Early in his career he was Assistant Chief of the Bank of Canada's Research Department where he advised the Governor and Bank of Canada management on economic conditions and the economic outlook.

Later as a partner with a national management consulting firm, Andersen was an economic consultant and advisor to a wide range of companies. He has always emphasized communication and the need to put economic analysis into terms that are useful for business decision-making.

Dr. Andersen also spent several years with several major Bay Street investment dealer firms before founding Andersen Economic Research Inc. His clients are widely distributed across a broad range of corporations and financial institutions throughout North America.

His objective is to act as a filter, separating the signals from the noise, in order to provide clients with the useful information that they really need. In his consulting practice, he provides strategic economic advice to senior management through boardroom meetings, video conferencing, email commentary, conference calls and the monthly Andersen Economic Report.

Looking to enhance your leadership skills and become a part of a community dedicated to leadership excellence?

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